

Emotional Intelligence and Organizational Performance in Commercial Banks in Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom State

Author's Details:

Abaikpa, Udeme Anthony

Department of Business Administration, Faculty of Management Sciences
Akwa Ibom State University, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria
udemeabaiakpa@gmail.com
+234-08063787705

Thomas, Cornelia David

Department of Management, Faculty of Social and Management Sciences
Ritman University, Ikot Ekpene, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.
thomas.cornelia@ritmanuniversity.edu.ng
+234-9098345556

Udoh, Unwana Nicholas

Department of Management, Faculty of Social and Management Sciences
Ritman University, Ikot Ekpene, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.
unwananicholas@gmail.com
+2348032276938

Dr. Udom Sunday Daniel

Department of Business Administration & Management, Faculty of Management Sciences
Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.
awesomeblisscharis@gmail.com
+2348038750959

Abstract

The study was designed to examine the relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Organizational Performance in commercial banks in Uyo Metropolis of Akwa Ibom State. A cross-sectional survey was adopted for the study and a sample of 162 respondents was drawn from the population of 271 using Taro Yamane's scientific sampling technique. For the objectives of the study to be achieved, two hypotheses were formulated and tested. The study utilized structured questionnaire and interview as the major instruments for data collection. 162 questionnaires were distributed and 135 were returned. Data were collected and analyzed using simple percentage and ordinal logistic regression. Results showed that there is a significant and positive relationship between variables of emotional intelligence such as self-control, self-management and, and employee performance in commercial banks in Uyo Metropolis of Akwa Ibom State. It was recommended that, self-control should be sustained by bank employees by continually developing the capacity to alter their thoughts, feelings, and behaviors to align them with organizational goals to enhance performance as well as developing the capacity to manage emotions as one of the major determinants of harmonious relationship among members in an organization.

Keywords: Emotional Intelligence, organizational performance, self-control, self-management.

1. INTRODUCTION

The relevance of emotional intelligence in achievement of organizational performance can never be under-estimated. This is because organization, like an organism is faced with several distinct stages of development; a moment of birth, growth, maturation and eventual end. Organizations' growth and success to a great extent is dependent on the strength and performance of their employees. Ordinarily, employee's exhibit positive as well as negative emotions at workplaces and these have great impact on the resultant outcomes as positive or negative respectively. Having a deep understanding and control over one's own emotions and understanding others' emotions is very vital for successful work relationships and creating conducive work

environment. Organizations should understand and accept that emotional intelligence is a key contributing factor to successful performance and strategize on inculcating emotional intelligence among their employees to create effective and efficient workplace. For several decades now, the challenge of achieving organizational performance has remained a contentious issue in service firms particularly commercial banks. This may not be unconnected to lack of proper management of employee emotional intelligence in such firms. Relatively, Goleman (2011) identifies several social skills which are components of emotional intelligence required by organizations to include self-control, self-management, relationship-management and employee competency. Several studies have identified that lack of self-control and effective management of emotions are some of the determinant factors of many commercial banks in Nigeria (Kalpana and Noopur, 2013; Shahram, 2013).

Evidently, one of the numerous ingredients for effective, healthy and competitive organization is a good self-management. In a very practical sense, it is most often observed that operations of organizations grind to a halt due to poor self-management of their employees. In concurring with the idea, Jain, et al., (2018) believe that efficient and effective service delivery is a function of proper employee self-management skills. Factors like misconceptions, poor mannerisms, wrong judgments as well as poor value systems may bring in chaos and anarchy in organizations. Similarly, (Adeniji and Akinbode, 2018, Odusina, 2014; Sanusi, 2012) believe that poor self-management skills among employees may influence an organizational output negatively. Emotional intelligence may be viewed as the capacity of recognizing our feelings and feelings of others, motivating ourselves and managing emotions in ourselves and in our relationships. The concept describes abilities distinct from but complementary to academic intelligence, the purely cognitive capacities measured by intelligence quotient (IQ). Relatively, Goleman (2011), describes emotional intelligence (EI) as the abilities to recognize, regulate and manage emotions in ourselves and in others. The concept has been viewed as the ability to monitor and manage one's own and others' emotions to discriminate between them and to use the information to guide one's thinking and actions (Kalpana and Noorpur, 2013). By implication, emotional intelligence might be considered as a group of individual competencies essentially required for the achievement of organizational performance. However, it is believed that organizations, particularly commercial banks that are conscious of the application of emotional intelligence in their operations are ones that have the abilities to satisfy their stakeholders, customers, employees, and other needs of the environment.

Moreover, it is believed that, the achievement of quality services in banking industry is not the result of a single causal factor but a result of the multiple factors which relationship management is significantly among such factors. In support of this notion, Reinartz et al., (2010) aver that an effective relationship management with the customers can strengthen a firm's market share and bring about long-term market leadership and mutual benefits between organization and customers. However, banks as the service providers are required to be adaptive towards the demands and behaviors of the customers through conscious application of emotional intelligence skills. It is believed that, basically, effective application of emotional intelligence skills such as relation management may help organizations particularly banks in responding effectively towards the customer needs. The learning and practice of emotional intelligence skills may help to improve the performance of service providers and thus increase customer satisfaction. A proper application and utilization of relationship management skills by organizations can help their increase knowledge about customers and give them greater ability for recognizing and regulating the quality of services according to the desires of customers.

The ability of an organization to recognize its competence as an intangible asset and manage it effectively may be viewed as one of the major contributing factors required for the achievement of organizational performance (Nayab, 2011). Recognizing and managing different dimensions of emotions is relevant and significant for measuring or predicting organizational performance and customers' satisfaction as most service delivery jobs require the ability to manage emotions. It is found that understanding the emotional intelligence level of employees may help an organization to achieve the desired outcome and provide suitable training to the managers and employees to regulate their emotions in order to help them to achieve the organizational objectives efficiently and effectively.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

The world over, most service organizations particularly banks are concerned with what should be done to help them achieve sustained high levels of performance. The banks belong to the service sector of the economy. It relates basically with humans. Most often, banking floors are characterized with loud shouts and complaints due to vast number of unsatisfied customers. Most often bank staff react to a “bad action” by a customer in a much uncivilized way. What could be responsible for this? Could this be attributed to lack of proper training of bank staff, especially on emotional intelligence? In some occasions, the branch managers or the operations manager would have to address some issues openly to maintain and sustain the smooth and hitch free operational atmosphere. However, for service delivery firms such as commercial banks to achieve their goal, they should look inward and ask themselves some pertinent questions such as: How well do we connect with our self and with others? To what extent is our ability to appropriately identify, recognize and manage our different dimensions of emotions for our own well-being as well as the wellbeing of people around us? This is because emotional intelligence as one of the innovative creativities in individuals or groups is believed to be very relevant in the achievement of organizational performance in-service delivery firms such as commercial banks, (Ganji 2011).

Many studies on emotional intelligence especially in service delivery firms such as commercial banks have identified some important gaps which are relevant factors which can ultimately decide the collective destiny of effective and successful organizations. Several of these studies concur that, the proper application and utilization of emotional intelligence skills such as self-control, self-management and relationship management could facilitate quality service delivery and performance realization within an organization, Hasanzadeh (2009). Many of these studies have shown that emotional intelligence has a direct link with organizational performance since employees have to deal with customers face to face. But many of these studies failed to include non-managerial employees in examining the effects of emotional intelligence on organizational performance. Also, many of these studies included only minimum number of performance measures in the analysis of organizational performance. Consequently, future studies should be extended to exploration of a wider range of employees at different organizational levels and researches on the relationship between emotional intelligence and multiple variables of job performance should be investigated. Thus, the relevance of emotional intelligence with regard to other predictors of performance should also be explored. It is against this background that, this study was designed to examine the relationship between emotional intelligence and organizational performance in commercial banks, Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom State. However, this is the gap the study was intended to cover.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study was to examine the relationship between emotional intelligence and organizational performance in commercial banks, Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom State. However, the study was designed to meet the following specific objectives:

- i. To examine the relationship between self-control and organizational performance in commercial banks, Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom State.
- ii. To assess the relationship between self-management and organizational performance in commercial banks, Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom State.

1.4 Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study:

- i. What is the relationship between self-control and organizational performance in commercial banks, Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom State?
- ii. To what extent is the relationship between self-management and organizational performance in commercial banks, Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom State?

1.5 Hypotheses

From the objectives of this study, the following research hypotheses were formulated to guide the study:

- i. Self-control has no significant relationship with organizational performance in commercial banks, Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom State.
- ii. Self-management has no significant relationship with organizational performance in commercial banks, Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom State.

2. REVIEW OF THE RELATED LITERATURE

2.1 Concept of Emotional Intelligence

The concept of emotional intelligence though is relatively recent behavioral concept prominent with Dr. Daniel Goleman's (1995) in his popular book called "Emotional Intelligence" has received an increasing attention in the literature of management and organizational behavior. According to Baron and Parker, (2010), the concept is traceable to the early studies in the 1920s. In the early 1980s, many scholars began to systematically conceptualize the term to include skill and competency management, Capaldo et al., (2016). Emotional development starts in the early period of an individual's life. Effective and healthy emotional development for an individual is relevant to both their ability to learn, when young and to their success and happiness as adults. In today's competitive business world, many organizations are beginning to recognize that having a high intelligence quotient is not enough, but high intelligent quotient with high emotional quotient makes an individual employee a good marketable product. This is because, as the business world is filled with competition, many organizations are expecting their employees to have different set of skills with required emotional abilities as well as intellectual ability in order to handle and balance all kinds of situations in work place. Emotional intelligence as the ability that comprises of set of emotional abilities such as self - control, self - management, relationship management, emotional sensitivity, emotional maturity and emotional competencies are constantly required of employees to assist organizations beat the competition.

Notably, Gardner's (2013) conceptualization of intrapersonal and interpersonal intelligence and other scholars' work on emotional literacy might be viewed as the building blocks for what is termed as emotional intelligence today. Based on this notion, (Baron 2010) views the concept of emotional intelligence as a cognitive intelligence which is defined as an array of personal and social abilities that could influence an individual's effective response to environmental demands and pressures. Deducing from several studies, emotional intelligence, therefore, may be viewed as the ability of recognizing our feelings and that of others in a group relationship. The concept can be described as ability distinct from, but complementary to academic intelligence, the purely cognitive capacities measured by intelligence quotient. A proper management of emotional intelligence may be viewed as a strategic advantage to an organization. This is because a competitive organization is one that has the ability to satisfy stakeholders, customers, employees, and other needs of the environment. And this could only be possible through proper management of emotional intelligence. Relatively, Goleman (2011), views emotional intelligence (EI) as the ability to recognize, regulate or manage emotions in ourselves and in others. For Salovey and Mayer (2009) the concept of emotional intelligence is viewed as the ability of an individual to observe his emotions and that of others, for the benefit of using them to control his actions in the organization. According to Goleman (2011) emotional intelligence might be considered as a group of individual competencies essential for organizational performance. By implication, poor management of emotional intelligence could affect individual and organizational success. However, based on popular opinion and workplace testimonials, emotional intelligence is argued as one of the factors that can improve organizational performance and productivity, (Lam and Kirby, 2012).

Similarly, Cherniss (2011) believes that emotional intelligence components like leadership, organizational climate and culture, individual emotional intelligence, group emotional intelligence, other human resource functions, result to relationships that give rise to organizational achievement of productivity. This means that, emotional intelligence may help organizational leaders to develop a vision for their organizations, motivate subordinates to commit to the vision and energize them to enthusiastically work to achieve this vision.

Moreover, emotional intelligence may enable managers to develop a unique identity for their organizations and instil in their employees a high level of trust while maintaining the flexibility needed to respond to changing conditions. In a related study, Mayer, et al (2010) defined emotional intelligence as the ability to adaptively perceive, understand and regulate emotions in oneself and in others. Several studies have revealed that people who are high in emotional intelligence get more success, make better interpersonal relation, work more effectively and spend healthy life than those people who are low in emotional intelligence, Roland (2011). However, for any organization, especially bank to achieve its productivity, the concept of emotional intelligence should be given an important consideration in human resources planning, job profiling, recruitment interviewing and selection, management development, customer relations and customer service delivery.

2.2 Self – control

Self-control is one of the defining qualities that distinguish human beings from other species of animals. Self-control is the capacity to alter one's thoughts, feelings, and behaviors to align them with one's goals (Goleman, 2011). Psychologists have viewed self-control from a variety of perspectives. Self-control may be referred to as one's ability to exercise restraint over their emotions in order to achieve the desired goals (Goleman, 2011). However, Schechtman, (2015) views the concept of self-control as a capacity most people have to a larger or lesser degree. According to Georgina (2014) self-control is one's ability to control emotional response to others by choosing correct emotional response and the concentration of this action. The concept of self-control in psychological literature involves the need to suppress immediate impulses or urges to act or react. Psychological literature has identified a number of processes that are involved in self-control. These processes are classed into four: i. Motivation, goals, and planning. ii. Attention allocation, iii. Cognitive change, and iv. Suppression. However, the line separating many of these categories is murky. This implies that, there are conceptual overlap or integration among the categories. People may have myriad of self-control tools at their disposal, but if they are not properly motivated to use those tools it is unlikely that they will exert self-control (Bonanno and Burton, 2013).

2.3 Self-Management

Self-Management may be defined as management by oneself, taking of responsibility for one's own behaviour and well-being within the organization. Employee self-management could be viewed as a form of organizational management based on self-directed work processes on the part of an organization's workforce. Self-management entails the capacity of a person to regulate his or her conduct with a tendency to pursue aims with purposeful energy and perseverance. Self-management could be viewed as a unique characteristic needed by an organization for the achievement of productivity. There are many variations of self-management. Members can manage themselves through grouping themselves while in other forms they can exercise authority through selection of specialists in the related field. However, self-management is made possible by these selected specialists from different fields within the organization.

Self-management may be viewed as the capacity of an employee to manage emotions as one of the major determinants of harmonious relationship among members in an organization (Nyerere and Barasa, 2015). Graham and Roger, (2018), describe employee self-management as the capacity for employees to efficiently utilize their mental functions of thinking such as understanding, observing and learning. The authors view employee self-management skills to entail the possession of skills such as self-awareness skills and other several social skills required by an organization. Jain, et al., (2018) describes the concept of self-management as efficient and effective management of employee skills. According to Adeniji and Akinbode, (2018) lack of efficient and effective employee self-management skills may affect organization's effectiveness. The goal of self-management is to grant workers autonomy in carrying out their operations in the organization. The action is designed to boost workers' morale and encourage sense of efficiency among them as part owners of the organization. According to Wu, (2010) employee self-management is not fixed and the same can be improved with different levels training. Michael, (2011) argues that most employees with high level of emotional

intelligence can utilize and regulate their own emotions and they have also the social competence and efficiency to manage others and maintain better relationships among themselves. By implication, those with high level of emotional intelligence are generally aware of how to manage their emotions in terms of retaining a positive mental state, a situation that can lead to increased efficiency. According to Wong (2017), an efficient management of employee emotional intelligence is a significant driver of organizational performance.

2.4 Organizational Performance

According to Kaplan and Norton (2012) organizational performance information is collated from four perspectives namely: the financial perspective, the customers' perspective, the internal business perspective, and innovation and learning perspective. They describe organizational performance model measures as consisted creativity, profitability, productivity, competitive advantage, effectiveness, efficiency, flexibility, quality, etc. Disciplinary problems, disputes, absenteeism, high labor turnover, fraud, low productivity, low profitability, poor service delivery to customers, suppressed creativity, innovation and learning influence performance. All these may culminate to poor organizational performance. According to (Cho et al, 2015) organizational performance can be related with variables like efficiency and effectiveness, employee motivation, job satisfaction, trust on employees etc. Organizational performance might not be achieved if employee performance is not given adequate attention by the organization. Adaptive employee performance is very important to organization. According to Baard, et al., (2014) an effective adaptive performance necessitates employees' ability to efficiently deal with volatile work circumstances. Griffin, et al., (2010) and Hollenbeck, et al., (2016) aver that, evolutions of various new occupations as an offshoot of technological innovation need employees to performance in a new dimension to be adaptable with changes. The employees are also expected to adjust their interpersonal behavior to work successfully with a wide range of peers and subordinates.

In the context of wholesome work performance, Griffin, et al., (2017) cited that, job proficiency could aid task performance, but adaptability and proactiveness to one's job role is important to address uncertain issues in business environments. Austin and Villanova, (2012) and Viswesvaran and Ones, (2010) opined that, along with the task and adaptability, efforts should be carried out toward ascertaining the significance of non-job components of performance to create a better workplace. Industrial psychologists have referred such non-job components as organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) or contextual performance that refers to voluntary actions of employees that benefit employers intangibly (Bateman and Organ, 2013). Brief and Motowidlo (2016) defines it as a behavior that is accomplished by an employee of an organization which is directed towards an individual, group or organization. Regarding the importance of voluntary work performance, psychologists view it as contextual performance (Borman and Motowidlo, 2017; Motowidlo and Van Scotter, 2014; Motowidlo, et al., 2017). It is believed that an engaged employee works with a sense of passion which leads to translation into not only high performance but extra role behavior as well, Kahn, (2010). Earlier researches in this context have advocated that growth in team spirit within an organization result in better employee performance and a happier workplace (Alie, et al., 2008; Boyt, et al., 2011; Cohen and Bailey, 2009). Contextual performance is a kind of attitude like volunteering for extra work (Coleman and Borman, 2010; Motowidlo and Schmit, 2009).

2.5 Theoretical Review

Theories are made to explain, predict and help to understand a concept or phenomenon. Theories help buttress existing knowledge within the limits of the critical bounding assumptions, David (2009). Consequently, the relationship between emotional intelligence and organizational performance may be best described and supported by the following theories:

2.6 Personality Theory

Personality theory is a theory that is based on individual traits which are attached to emotional intelligence in individuals. It is made up of a range of emotional dispositions and competencies such as self-

control, self-management, relationship management, enthusiasm, empathy and adeptness in relationships. Accordingly, these traits predispose an individual to act in definite manner in different situations which McCrae and Oliver (1992) identified as the big five personality model namely, openness to experience, conscientiousness, extraversion, neuroticism and agreeableness. However, traits attributed to individuals are an attempt to know why or why not they behave in a particular way. This is no doubt influenced by their cognitive ability and signals a sensation of order which can appear baseless and awkward. In line with this, personality theory categorizes people into types on the basis of personality tests and identifies types of people along extraversion or introversion. Practically, personality theory explains the relationship between employees' emotions and their performance in organizations.

2.7 Bar-On Model of Emotional-Social Intelligence

The model of emotional-social intelligence by Bar-On (1997) defines emotional intelligence as a set of non-cognitive capabilities that influences one's ability in coping with environmental demands. Bar-On's model explains why individuals with emotional intelligence tend to succeed in life and at work more than others. This model predicts success at home, at school, and at work and help to discourage aggressiveness and rudeness among employees and youths. (Goleman, 2011).

2.8 The Mental Ability Model

The mental ability model of emotional intelligence is cognition based. It focuses on how emotions affect thinking, adaptive behaviour, and decision-making. This model focuses on non- verbal perception or empathy, Mayer and Cobb, (2010). Mental ability helps to identify and deal effectively with emotions, Mayer and Cobb (2010). The mental ability model predicts that people who are emotionally intelligent are more likely to have grown up in bio-socially adaptive households. They are non-defensive, able to reframe their emotions effectively, choose good emotional role model, able to communicate and discuss feelings, and develop expert knowledge in a particular emotional area (Mayer and Salovey, 2011).

2.9 Goleman Model of Emotional Intelligence

The Goleman model is one of the recent theoretical models of emotional intelligence developed by Daniel Goleman in 1995. Goleman developed a framework of five key components that make up emotional intelligence, plus a range of skills that can be developed and improved, so as to make it possible for anyone to become more emotionally intelligent. The components comprised self-awareness, self-regulation, motivation, empathy and social skills. Goleman believed that, as a manager or an employee, one can apply emotional intelligence to achieve self-awareness, objectivity and equality and improve results in organization. He believed that, employees who are self-aware would know and feel comfortable with themselves. Goleman believed that, a manager in a bad mood, with no self-awareness, makes bad and biased choices and a manager, in a bad mood with heightened self-awareness realises and isolates negativity, refocusing on the task at hand. Put it differently, the Goleman model explains that, a manager or an employee who is self-aware can know when he needs help, from who and how, and can apply this technique to effect changes.

Goleman defines self-regulation as a skill employee need to practice and there are great rewards if they can practice and master it. Goleman views self-regulation as the ability to be calm in the face of adversity. He believes that, self-regulation makes employees become approachable, able to deal with conflict, create a nurturing environment and lead by reliable example. Goleman's motivation for enjoyment rather than money or a promotion is the third component. Self-motivation here means that, even in the face of a bad day, a manager or an employee can still find the silver lining, feel energized to fix problems and determined to cheer the people around him unto the next level of goal attainment. Self-motivation would help a manager as well as employee to fulfil their personal goals and needs and also help to drive higher performance.

Goleman believes that being a good listener, interpreter, attuned to body language and expressions are the attributes of empathetic manager. He believes that, a manager or an employee who can understand the emotions of others and relate with them can help him see and solve their problems. An empathic manager or

employee is considerate, balanced, and fair. Applying empathy gives a manager an opportunity to know what his group members are going through. Goleman believes that as a manager, social skills is important to build a strong rapport with your team. Goleman believes that emotional intelligence skills are both inborn and learned and can be developed through both formal and informal life experiences, Goleman, (2011). But some researchers have found a genetic link to these skills that nature plays a role in emotional intelligence development (Goleman, 2011).

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

Research design constitutes the blue print, plans and guidelines that is used in data collection and analyses with regard to the study. Research design is a must step requirement for a research process if research problems and hypotheses are to be adequately addressed. Therefore, this study employed a cross-sectional survey.

3.2 The Study Area

This study was conducted in Akwa Ibom State. The study covered five banks namely: First bank, Access bank, UBA, ECO bank and Zenith bank in Akwa Ibom State. These banks were selected according to old and new generation basis. The State is in the South-South zone of Nigeria with its capital at Uyo. The State is the largest oil producing state in Nigeria. The population of the State is estimated at about 309, 573 as of 2006 (NPC, 2006 report). It has a land area of 95km² (36. 7sq.ml), Wikipedia encyclopedia (2007). The people in the area are predominantly Ibibio; others include Annang, Oron, Eket, Obolo, Ibeno and other speaking tribes in Nigeria. Akwa Ibom State is inhabited by people of different walks of life such as teachers, businessmen, students, traders, civil servants and unemployed youths among others. The choice of this study area was driven by the relevance of the research topic.

3.3 Population

The population of this study consisted 271 staff of the selected banks using their banks' staff nominal roll of 2023. The distribution of the population is as shown in table below:

Table 1
Distribution of population by Banks

S/n	Bank	population
1.	First bank	75
2.	ECO bank	33
3.	Access bank	46
4.	UBA	69
5.	Zenith bank	48
	Total	271

Source: Record of staff nominal roll, 2023.

3.4 Sample Size/Sampling Technique

As a result of the inability of the researcher to effectively study the entire staff population of the selected banks, a representative number of 162 was chosen as sample size population. The sample size was calculated using Taro Yamane's scientific formula which is given as:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where:

$$\begin{aligned}
 N &= \text{Population} \\
 1 &= \text{constant} \\
 e &= \text{Level of significance} \\
 n &= \text{sample size} \\
 n &= \frac{271}{1 + 271 (0.0025)} \\
 n &= \frac{271}{1.6775} \\
 n &= 162
 \end{aligned}$$

3.5 Sources of Data Collection

Data for this research work were collected through two sources – primary and secondary sources. The primary data were obtained by the researcher through questionnaire administration and personal interviews. Secondary data were obtained from published reports, books, journals, newspapers, magazines and internet.

3.6 Instrument for Data Collection

An emotional intelligence and organizational performance questionnaire was used as an instrument for data collection. The questionnaire was divided into two sections. Section A and section B. Section A dealt with information on the demographic data of the respondents. Section B will be the main body of the questionnaire. This section contained twenty (20) closed-ended questions using a five-point Likert' scale instrument through which the opinions of the respondents were expressed. Their responses were measured by means of a five-category rating system as follows:

SA	-	Strongly agree
A	-	Agree
D	-	Disagree
SD	-	Strongly disagree
U	-	Undecided

3.7 Validity of Research Instrument

The validity is basically concerned on how a research instrument measures what it intended to measure (Field, 2005). Consequently, the researcher was concerned with the degree to which the instrument measured emotional intelligence and organizational performance. Face validity of the questionnaire was established in order to make sure that the questionnaire items appear to take care of relevant information in the area of interest. The face validity of the questionnaire was established by the researcher's supervisors and experts in the Department of Business Administration, Akwa Ibom State University. Each sub - section in the questionnaire has five items which were reviewed by the experts and all ambiguous items were removed and those found relevant were retained. The experts certified that the instrument was face valid and should be used for the study.

3.8 Reliability of the Instrument

A test is said to be reliable if it measures what it is supposed to measure consistently (Huck, 2007). In order to determine the reliability of the research instrument used in the study, the corrected questionnaire was administered randomly on selected staff of Keystone bank and Wema bank in Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom State. This approach was repeated with the same groups after one-month period and the results obtained from the first and second pre-test were consistent, then, the instrument is was be said to be reliable.

3.9 Procedure for data Collection/Administration of the Instrument

Data collection was done in the banks under study. The researcher visited the banks with letter from the supervisor to obtain permission from the banks and clarified the motivation behind the study to them. Relevant information for the study was gathered by the researcher with the assistance of the operations managers in each

of the banks. The staff were informed of the activity and the need to give honest responses to the instructions that data collected would be used and treated confidentially for academic research purposes only. After this, the researcher undertook the administration of the questionnaire to respondents with the help of research assistant in each of the banks used for the study. These were distributed between November - December 2021 on the 1st semester of 2020/2021 academic year.

3.10 Methods of Data Analysis

Considering the nature of data collected, the statistical methods adopted for data analysis was the ordinal logistic regression. This tool was adopted based on non-parametric analysis – ordinal scale data. The data were analyzed with the help of a statistical tool using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS).

4. DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS

4.1 Data Presentation

The data presented contained responses to the items in the questionnaire and the computed data for variables of the study. The data on the items are based on the five-point Likert scale used in scoring the instrument. The sampled number of questionnaires administered to the selected bank staff were collected and presented as shown in Table 4.1 below:

Table 4.1: Data Presentation on Distribution of Sampled Questionnaire by Banks

Bank	Number of Sampled questionnaires Distributed	Number of Sampled questionnaires Returned
First Bank	33 (20.37%)	30(18.52%)
ECO Bank	33 (20.37%)	27(16.67%)
Access Bank	32 (19.75%)	28(17.28%)
UBA	33 (20.37%)	24(14.81%)
Zenith Bank	31(19.14%)	26(16.05%)
Total	162(100%)	135(83.33%)
Total Number of Sampled questionnaire discarded and not Returned		27(16.67%)

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 4.1 depicts that out of the total of 162 questionnaires distributed to selected bank staff, 135 questionnaires representing 83.33% were correctly filled and returned, 27 questionnaires representing 16.67% were both discarded and not returned. Therefore, the researcher collected a total number of 135 questionnaires and the collated data from the respondents were used for the analysis. Furthermore, Table 4.2 presents the respondents' demographics because in qualitative research that involves the analysis of subjective opinions of the respondents, it is important to know the physiognomies of the respondents and how their responses can help in solving the research problem.

Table 4.1.1: Data Presentation on Respondents' Demographics

Demographics	Options	Frequency	Percentage
GENDER	Male	66	48.9
	Female	69	51.14
	Total	135	100.00
AGE GROUP	51 and above	13	9.63
	41 – 50	19	14.07
	36 – 40	21	15.56
	31- 35	29	21.48
	21-30	38	28.15
	15-20	15	11.11
	Total	135	100.0
MARITAL STATUS	Widowed	2	1.5

	Divorced	5	3.7
	Separated	21	15.6
	Married	51	37.8
	Singled	56	41.5
	Total	135	100.0
EDUCATIONAL QUALIFICATION	Ph.D.	9	6.67
	M.Sc./MBA	15	11.11
	HND/B.Sc.	46	34.07
	OND/NCE	49	36.30
	SSCE	16	11.85
	Total	135	100.0
YEARS OF EXPERIENCE	15 and above	51	37.80
	12 – 14	58	43.00
	9 – 11	9	6.70
	6 – 8	9	6.70
	3 – 5	3	2.20
	0 – 2	5	3.70
	Total	135	100.00
RANK	Junior Staff	83	61.5
	Senior Staff	31	23.0
	Management Staff	21	15.6
	Total	135	100.0

Source: Field Survey Data (2023)

From Table 4.1.1, a total of 69 respondents representing 51.1% were female while a total of 66 representing 48.9% of the respondents were male. This implied that majority of the participants were female. However, this does not presuppose the fact that using more women in the study will in any way affect the analysis and findings of the study. This is because the opinions expressed are highly likely to represent general opinion or position concerning the research issues and not depending on feminine or masculine opinion or position. Also, the majority of the respondents (28.15%) were under the age bracket between 21 – 30 years. Majority of the respondents 56 (41.5%) were single as well as OND/NCE holders as evidenced in 36.30%. Majority of the respondents 58 (43%) have working experience spanning between 12-14years. The responses to the questions on the research constructs are presented in Table 4.1.2, which contains questions on the items measuring each research construct or variable and the responses. The data on the items are presented in nominal scale to reflect the scoring.

Table 4.1.2: Data Presentation on research items and constructs

RESEARCH STATEMENTS / ITEMS	SA	A	SD	D	N
SELF-CONTROL DIMENSION					
Promotion in my bank is judged based self-control.	28(20.70%)	32(23.70%)	26(19.30%)	27(20%)	22(16.30%)
My bank productivity is high due to good behavior of staff.	35(25.9%)	56(41.5%)	25(18.5%)	12(8.9%)	7(5.2%)
Staffs in my bank are not aggressive with their customers.	30(22.2%)	65(48.1%)	26(19.3%)	10(7.4%)	4(3.0%)
Staff in my bank easily cope with environmental pressures.	35(25.9%)	56(41.5%)	25(18.5%)	12(8.9%)	7(5.2%)
Staffs in my bank are always polite when reacting to customers.	35(25.9%)	56(41.5%)	25(18.5%)	12(8.9%)	7(5.2%)
SELF-MANAGEMENT DIMENSION					
Staffs in my bank have social skills of managing themselves.	57(42.2%)	47(34.8%)	14(10.4%)	8(5.9%)	9(6.7%)
There is a good level interpersonal relationship in my bank due to good self-management of staff.	66(48.9%)	45(33.3%)	13(9.6%)	4(3.0%)	7(5.2%)
My bank achieves high performance due to good staff self-management.	58(43.0%)	55(40.7%)	13(9.6%)	5(3.7%)	4(3.0%)

Employee satisfaction is high in my bank due to good self-management policies.	42(31.1%)	63(46.7%)	13(9.6%)	12(8.9%)	5(3.7%)
My bank has fair policies for every employee.	57(42.2%)	47(34.8%)	14(10.4%)	8(5.9%)	9(6.7%)
ORGANIZATIONAL PERFORMANCE DIMENSION					
Quality service delivery in my bank is high	37(27.4%)	45(33.3%)	18(13.3%)	22(16.3%)	13(9.6%)
My bank is very effective in achieving results	42(31.1%)	54(40.0%)	20(14.8%)	11(8.1%)	8(5.9%)
My bank's control of market is high	26(19.3%)	45(33.3%)	20(14.8%)	31(23.0%)	13(9.6%)
My bank is very efficient	25(18.5%)	28(20.7%)	27(20.0%)	31(23.0%)	24(17.8%)
My bank's growth index is high	34(25.2%)	38(28.1%)	21(15.6%)	23(17.0%)	19(14.1%)

Source: Field Survey Data (2023).

4.2 Data Analysis

The responses to the various questions on the items measuring each construct as presented above in Table 4.1.7 are analyzed in this section followed by descriptive statistics analysis.

4.3 Self-control and organizational performance in commercial banks, Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom State

The first objective was on the relationship between self-control and organizational performance in commercial banks, Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom State. This implies that respondents were asked several questions linking self-control to organizational performance. Table 4.3 shows that majority of respondents gave affirmation that promotion in their bank is judged based on self-control, as evidenced in the 32 respondents representing 23.70% that agreed to the claim. Also, it was revealed that 56 respondents representing 41.5% agreed that their bank productivity is high due to good behavior of staff. Furthermore, 65 respondents representing 48.1% agreed that staffs in their bank are not aggressive with their customers. 41.5% of the respondents agreed that staff in their easily cope with environmental pressures while another 41.5% of the respondents agreed staffs in their bank are always polite when reacting to customers. However, this finding is subject to scientific testing and until such test is conducted, it becomes valid.

4.4 Self-management and organizational performance in commercial banks, Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom State

The second objective was on the relationship between self-management and organizational performance in commercial banks, Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom State. This infers that respondents were asked several questions linking self-management to organizational performance. Table 4.1.7 displays that majority of respondents strongly agreed that staffs in their bank have social skills of managing themselves, as shown in the 57 respondents representing 42.2%. Also, it was discovered that 66 respondents representing 48.9% strongly agreed that there is a good level of interpersonal relationship in their bank due to good self-management of staff. Moreover, 58 respondents representing 43% strongly agreed that their bank achieves high performance due to good staff self-management while 63(46.7%) respondents agreed that employee satisfaction is high in their bank due to good self-management policies. 57(42.2%) of the respondents strongly agreed that their bank has fair policies for every employee. Nevertheless, this finding is subject to scientific testing and until such test is conducted, it becomes valid.

4.5 Descriptive analyses of research variables

This analysis was conducted to assess the descriptive properties of the research variables in order to ascertain if the data possess requisite characteristics for statistical analysis. These analyses involve descriptive statistics such as the mean, standard deviation, minimum, maximum as well as skewness and kurtosis. This statistic discloses the characteristics of the research variables principally in terms of variance or closeness of the data points to the mean. The ultimate is to determine the degree of variability of the data away from the mean. A high variability indicates high degree of variance and high potential of non-normality of the data thus leading to

unreliable estimate. It is desired that the dataset has low level of variability. Table 4.1.7 presents the result of this statistics.

Table 4.5: Descriptive Statistics Result

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness		Kurtosis	
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error
Organizational performance	135	2.00	5.00	3.8246	.69580	-.508	.210	-.242	.417
Self-control	135	1.25	5.00	4.0685	.68800	-1.218	.209	1.788	.414
Self-management	135	1.25	5.00	4.0185	.73975	-1.308	.209	2.328	.414

Source: Researcher’s Computation (2023) from SPSS Output.

From the result in Table 4.5, all mean values fall in between the maximum and minimum values of 5 and 4.06 respectively. Again, the standard deviations values for all variables are less than 1, which indicate low variance. This shows that the data points of the variables are clustered around the mean and is highly likely to be the true position of the opinions expressed and the parameters estimated with this data set is highly likely to have less or minimal error.

4.6 Test of Hypotheses

This section presents the test result of the hypotheses developed to guide the conduct of this study. This test was performed with simple regression statistics. The essence of the tests is to examine the nature of the relationship that exists between the independent and dependent variable.

4.7 Hypothesis I

The first hypothesis (Ho₁) was that: *Self-control has no significant relationship with organizational performance in commercial banks, Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom State.* This hypothesis was tested using simple regression statistics and the results are presented in Table 4.2.1.

Table 4.7: Regression Results for Hypothesis I

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.286 ^a	.082	.075	.76236

a. Predictors: (Constant), Self-control

b. Dependent Variable: Organizational performance

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	6.773	1	6.773	11.653	.001 ^b
	Residual	76.136	131	.581		
	Total	82.909	132			

a. Dependent Variable: Organizational performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), Self-control

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.182	.371		5.887	.000
	Self-control	.326	.095	.286	3.414	.001

a. Dependent Variable: Organizational performance

Source: Researcher’s Computation (2023) from SPSS Output.

From the result in Table 4.7, it was found, on average that for every 1% change in self-control, organizational performance in commercial banks, Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom State will increase by about 32.6%, and this change is significant at 1% level. With this result, the null hypothesis that “*Self-control has no significant relationship with organizational performance in commercial banks, Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom State*”, is rejected in this study. This means that self-control has no significant relationship with organizational performance in commercial banks, Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom State. In quantitative perspective, as indicated by the t-value 3.414, this would mean that an increase in self-control will lead to about 3.414 more organizational performance in commercial banks, Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom State. The f-stat value (11.653) which is significant at 1% level implies that the model returning this result is correct and valid. The R² value of 0.82 implies that the model explains a total of 82% of the variation in the dependent variable while 18% of the variation is explained by variables not included in the model.

4.8 Hypothesis II

The second hypothesis (Ho₂) was that: “*Self-management has no significant relationship with organizational performance in commercial banks, Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom State*”. This hypothesis was tested using simple regression statistics and the results are presented in Table 4.8.

Table 4.8: Regression Results for Hypothesis II

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.094 ^a	.009	.001	.62523	1.665

a. Predictors: (Constant), Self-management

b. Dependent Variable: Organizational performance

ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	.459	1	.459	1.174	.281 ^b
Residual	51.992	133	.391		
Total	52.451	134			

a. Dependent Variable: Organizational performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), Self-management

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	3.837	.240		15.987	.000
Self-management	.074	.068	.094	1.083	.281

Dependent Variable: Organizational performance

Predictor;(Constant), Self-management

Source: Researcher’s Computation (2023) from SPSS Output.

From the result in Table 4.2.2, it was found, on average that for every 1% change in self-management, organizational performance in commercial banks, Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom State will increase by about 0.074%, and this change is insignificant at 1% level. With this result, the null hypothesis that “*Self-management has no significant relationship with organizational performance in commercial banks, Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom State*”, is accepted in this study. In quantitative perspective, as indicated by the t-value 1.083, this would mean that an increase in self-management will lead to about 1.1 more organizational performance in commercial banks in Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom State. The R^2 value of 0.009 implies that the model explains a total of 0.09% of the variation in the dependent variable while 99.91% of the variation is explained by variables not included in the model. The D-W stat. value of 1.665 is above 1.5 and is thus closer to 2 indicating the absence of autocorrelation problem in the estimated parameters. The economic implication of the result is that improvement in organizational performance in commercial banks in Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom State can be achieved if greater efforts are channeled to self-management.

4.9 Discussion of Findings

4.10 The relationship between self-control and organizational performance in commercial banks, Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom State.

The results of the regression analysis were presented in Table 4.10. From the results, it was found, on average that for every 1% change in self-control, organizational performance in commercial banks, Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom State would increase by about 32.6%, and this change is significant at 1% level. Based on the t-value of 3.414, which is significant at 1% level, the finding was that self-control has no significant relationship with organizational performance in commercial banks, Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom State. This finding is inconsistent with the finding of (Bonanno and Burton, 2013) who believe that the proper use of self-control has a significant and positive influence on employee performance. From the interview responses, there seemed to be relationship between the employees' self-control and their performance.

4.11 The relationship between self-management and organizational performance in commercial banks, Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom State.

The results of the regression analysis were presented in Table 4.11. From the results, it was found, on average that for every 1% change in self-management, organizational performance in commercial banks, Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom State would increase by about 0.074%, and this change is insignificant at 1% level. Based on the t-value of 1.083, which is insignificant at 1% level, the finding was that self-management has no significant relationship with organizational performance in commercial banks, Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom State. This finding is inconsistent with the finding of Graham and Roger (2018) that employee self-management could impact positively on organizational performance. But from the interview with respondents, it was evident that there is a significant relationship between self-management and employee performance in commercial banks in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State.

5. SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Summary of the Findings

The main objective of this study was to examine the relationship between emotional intelligence and organizational performance in commercial banks, Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom State. The specific objectives of the research were to examine the relationship between self-control and organizational performance in commercial banks, Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom State; assess the relationship between self-management and organizational performance in commercial banks, Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom State. Two hypotheses were formulated and tested in this study. The researcher employed a cross-sectional survey design in which primary data were obtained through questionnaire administration and interview. The reported t-value output from a

simple regression technique was used to test the hypotheses of the study. The findings of the study were summarized as follows:

- i. Self-control has a significant relationship with organizational performance in commercial banks, Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom State.
- ii. Self-management has no significant relationship with organizational performance in commercial banks, Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom State.

5.2 Conclusion

The findings showed that self-control has a significant relationship with organizational performance in commercial banks, Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom State. This simply means that self-control is one's ability to exercise restraint over their emotions in order to achieve the desired goals. Self-control may also be viewed as a capacity most people have to a larger or lesser degree as well as one's ability to control emotional response to others by choosing correct emotional response and the concentration of this action. These abilities exerted have the probability of influencing organizational performance in a positive way. Further finding revealed that self-management has no significant relationship with organizational performance in commercial banks, Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom State. Lack of efficient and effective employee self-management skills may affect organization's effectiveness and performance. The goal of self-management is to grant workers autonomy in carrying out their operations in the organization. The action is designed to boost workers' morale and encourage sense of efficiency among them as part owners of the organization. One of ostensible reasons why self-management has no significant relationship with organizational performance is the fact that employee self-management is not fixed and the same can be improved with different levels of training in order to improve organizational performance.

5.3 Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

- i. Self-control should be sustained by bank employees by continually developing the capacity to alter one's thoughts, feelings, and behaviors to align them with organizational goals to enhance performance.
- ii. There is need for employee to develop the capacity to manage emotions as one of the major determinants of harmonious relationship among members in an organization.

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APPENDIX I

Please read carefully each of the statement below and tick to indicate your agreement or disagreement to each item. Each item has to do with the level of relationship between emotional intelligence and organizational performance. The level or degrees of your responses are: Strongly agree (SA), Agree (A), strongly disagree (SD), disagree (D) and Neutral (N).

S/N	VARIABLES	SA	A	SD	D	N
A	SELF-CONTROL DIMENSION					
1	Promotion in my bank is judged based self-control.					
2	My bank productivity is high due to good behavior of staff.					
3	Staffs in my bank are not aggressive with their customers.					
4	Staff in my bank easily cope with environmental pressures.					
5	Staffs in my bank are always polite when reacting to customers.					
B	SELF-MANAGEMENT DIMENSION					
6	Staffs in my bank have social skills of managing themselves.					
7	There is a good level interpersonal relationship in my bank due to good self-management of staff.					
8	My bank achieves high performance due to good staff self-management.					
9	Employee satisfaction is high in my bank due to good self-management policies.					
10	My bank has fair policies for every employee.					
F	ORGANIZATIONAL PERFORMANCE DIMENSION					
26	Quality service delivery in my bank is high					
27	My bank is very effective in achieving results					
28	My bank's control of market is high					
29	My bank is very efficient					
30	My bank's growth index is high					

FIELD SURVEY DATA

RESEARCH STATEMENTS / ITEMS	SA	A	SD	D	N
SELF-CONTROL DIMENSION					
Promotion in my bank is judged based self-control.	28(20.70%)	32(23.70%)	26(19.30%)	27(20%)	22(16.30%)
My bank productivity is high due to good behavior of staff.	35(25.9%)	56(41.5%)	25(18.5%)	12(8.9%)	7(5.2%)
Staffs in my bank are not aggressive with their customers.	30(22.2%)	65(48.1%)	26(19.3%)	10(7.4%)	4(3.0%)
Staff in my bank easily cope with environmental pressures.	35(25.9%)	56(41.5%)	25(18.5%)	12(8.9%)	7(5.2%)
Staffs in my bank are always polite when reacting to customers.	35(25.9%)	56(41.5%)	25(18.5%)	12(8.9%)	7(5.2%)
SELF-MANAGEMENT DIMENSION					
Staffs in my bank have social skills of managing themselves.	57(42.2%)	47(34.8%)	14(10.4%)	8(5.9%)	9(6.7%)
There is a good level interpersonal relationship in my bank due to good self-management of staff.	66(48.9%)	45(33.3%)	13(9.6%)	4(3.0%)	7(5.2%)
My bank achieves high performance due to good staff self-management.	58(43.0%)	55(40.7%)	13(9.6%)	5(3.7%)	4(3.0%)
Employee satisfaction is high in my bank due to good self-management policies.	42(31.1%)	63(46.7%)	13(9.6%)	12(8.9%)	5(3.7%)
My bank has fair policies for every employee.	57(42.2%)	47(34.8%)	14(10.4%)	8(5.9%)	9(6.7%)
ORGANIZATIONAL PERFORMANCE DIMENSION					
Quality service delivery in my bank is high	37(27.4%)	45(33.3%)	18(13.3%)	22(16.3%)	13(9.6%)
My bank is very effective in achieving results	42(31.1%)	54(40.0%)	20(14.8%)	11(8.1%)	8(5.9%)
My bank's control of market is high	26(19.3%)	45(33.3%)	20(14.8%)	31(23.0%)	13(9.6%)
My bank is very efficient	25(18.5%)	28(20.7%)	27(20.0%)	31(23.0%)	24(17.8%)
My bank's growth index is high	34(25.2%)	38(28.1%)	21(15.6%)	23(17.0%)	19(14.1%)